

Investigating journalists' lack of access to information from Afghan government agencies

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Abstract

The right to access information is one of the major challenges in developing countries, including Afghanistan. In such systems, governments prevent citizens from accessing information for a variety of reasons, including the confidentiality of information and the protection of national interests and national security or the protection of privacy. Unfortunately, in Afghanistan, due to the weak rule of law, the foundations of the legitimacy of the system are not strong and solid, corruption, selfishness and ethnicity are rampant in the administration, etc. Therefore, the implementation of the law on access to information with serious challenges and obstacles. Encounters. This article will try to identify the reasons for people not having access to information and also clarify why institutions are not willing to respond and do not share information with the media despite the passage of the law on the right to access information and what will be the solution.

Keywords: Journalists, Information, Afghanistan, law, administration.

Introduction

The free flow of information is one of the foundations of democracy that has received special attention in the last three decades, and this attention stems from the fact that the stability and consistency of democracy in the current era is impossible without the free flow of information. For this reason, many scholars have referred to the right to free access and dissemination of information to the oxygen of democracy. The people's right to access information increases the level of knowledge and awareness of the people and strengthens the people's trust in the government apparatus and encourages them to participate in national decisions and programs. Therefore, paying attention to the concept of freedom of information and the right of access to it is very important from the perspective of the relationship between the people and political power. Access to information accelerates the process of innovation and initiative in society and identifies talents and brings them to maturity and growth.

On the other hand, power and information are organically and directly related to each other. A democratic system is possible when the extent of government power over its citizens is reduced. People's sovereignty is strengthened when the people are aware of the government's policies, programs and decisions and can react to them. Thus, the right to access information, on the one hand, creates the necessary mechanism for the realization of citizens' rights, and on the other hand, guarantees law-based behavior and the exercise of legitimate government power. Therefore, due to the importance of the subject, this research can provide the necessary information on the implementation and challenges that limit it and why information does not leak

from institutions, and finally this research will provide an opportunity. To increase people's knowledge about it so that I can achieve good governance.

Problem statement

Although freedom of expression and the media and the right of citizens to access information are recognized in the Afghan constitution; But due to the lack of a legal mechanism, this right has been ignored by government agencies and private institutions.

Citizens need access to tools for active participation in national processes. Access to information is an inevitable part of people's political participation in public processes. Journalists also need reliable and accurate information to cover news and reports related to internal issues, and this information should be provided to government officials by the media, which unfortunately has not been the case so far, and government officials have always refused to provide information to The media has refused.

For this reason, journalists and media outlets have always criticized the actions of government officials in this regard, calling their refusal to provide information to the people a violation of human rights, a violation of the constitution, and a disregard for the principle of freedom of expression.

At present, although we have the law on the right of access to information and the legislative decrees to implement it, the people and the media still face the same problems as before and are deprived of the right of access to information.

Research Hypothesis:

It is thought that the authorities in the Afghan political system are not very interested in providing information about their performance to the people.

Main question:

1-Do the authorities want to make information about their performances available to the people, especially the media?

Sub-question:

- 1- Why information is not leaked from offices?
- 2 - Why do not the authorities want or are not interested in providing information about their performance?
- 3- What information do the authorities want to make available to the media?

Necessity of research

The importance and necessity of this research can be considered as follows:

- 1- This article has helped in the process of knowing and implementing the law of the right of access to information, because this issue increases the level of knowledge and awareness of the people about obeying the law.
- 2- Strengthens the right of access to information, people's beliefs and trust in the government apparatus.
- 3- Access to information accelerates the process of creativity and initiative in society and identifies talents and leads them to maturity and growth.
4. Ensuring the right of access to information is, in fact, the realization of one of the rights of citizens and, on the other hand, guarantees law-based behavior and the exercise of the legitimate power of the government.

Research purposes

In fact, the purpose of this research is the following:

- 1- Encouraging the authorities to provide information about their performances to the people.
- 2- Informing and informing about the right of access to information in the country.
- 3- Promoting the culture of obeying the law in the country.
- 4- Institutionalization of open governance or good and accountable governance.

background research

No research has been done on this issue so far. Of course, some of the writings on this subject are available in foreign languages and some researches have been written in national languages, which is not enough, and this research will look at this issue from the angles that It is different from other writings.

Research Methodology

The method I want to use in this research paper will be survey and library method.

Research structure

The structure of this article will be descriptive and analytical.

Theoretical concepts

Access to information is one of the major challenges in developing countries, including Afghanistan. Governments prevent citizens from accessing information for a variety of reasons, including the confidentiality of information and the protection of national interests and national security or the protection of privacy. Usually in countries like Afghanistan where the rule of law is weak, the foundations of the legitimacy of the system are not strong, corruption, selfishness and ethnicity are rampant in the administration, so all areas of life, especially freedom of expression, in other words; The law on access to information faces serious challenges and obstacles. While the law on dissemination and access to information leads to social cohesion and the development of national security, and causes transparency and accountability of government institutions to the people, and increases people's trust in the government; Conversely, disinformation is in fact a censorship that brings darkness. (Ahang, 1393: 114-116).

Undoubtedly, the dissemination of information to create transparency, accountability and democracy in political systems is a prerequisite, and as we have said, the media, as a watchdog, monitors the situation of the government in order to inform the citizens about the situation and the government in front of accountable citizens. (Sipasgar. 1384: 44).

Therefore, the mission of the media is to provide accurate information about the events and actions and decisions of the government with the principle of observance of objectivity, fairness, impartiality and balance and present it to the people to increase the enlightenment of society and the government to make mistakes. Build it and provide the right path and grounds for the prosperity of the country. (Bernardi. 1383: 4).

Definition of freedom of information

Information means any kind of data, document, file and information that can be provided and transferred to another. Freedom of information means the search, collection, transfer, dissemination and free receipt of information, information, news and ideas.

Historically, the "right of access to information" has been one of the components of freedom of information that has been used almost synonymously for the last three decades. (Rahmani, 1397: 71-73).

However, the history of the right of people to access information can be traced back to ancient Greece and traced back to Aristotle's thoughts and ideas; But what gave this right a legal dimension and helped to spread this right globally was the International Summit on Freedom of Information in 1948, which was held in Geneva

with the participation of 51 UN member states. At this meeting, Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights was drafted and approved a few months later.

The right to freedom of expression, as enshrined in Article 19, contains a positive element and obliges governments to take the necessary steps to ensure that it is respected. (Motamed Nejad, 1393: 434-435).

This article emphasizes the need for freedom of information and communication, stating that every person has the right to receive, search, transmit and disseminate information. The provisions of Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights are as follows:

1. No one shall be subjected to arbitrary interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to attacks upon his honor and reputation.
2. Everyone has the right to freedom of expression, including the right to seek, receive and impart information and ideas of all kinds, regardless of frontiers, either orally, in writing, in print, in art or by any other means of choice. It is itself. (Alam, 1388: 22-28).

Today, free access to information is considered one of the elements of the realization of freedom of expression and freedom of the mass media, that is, until the mass media and mass media in the world are minimally developed, the expectation of free flow of information will be no more. (Fanoos, 1393: 3-5).

Article 50 of the Afghan Constitution authorizes Afghan citizens to have access to public information. The rights of others and public security are unlimited, and Afghan citizens are eligible for government service without discrimination and in accordance with the law. (Justice, Ministry. 2003: Article 50).

In addition to the provisions of the Constitution, Article 5 of the Afghanistan Media Law of 2009 explicitly states the right of access to information:

"Everyone has the right to demand and receive information. The government provides the requested information at the request of its citizens, unless the requested information is a confidential secret and its disclosure would jeopardize the security, national interests and territorial integrity of the country." Encounter or harm the rights of others. (Ministry of Justice 1388: 9).

Article 4 of the Law on the Right to Access to Information, signed by President Ghani in 2014, also states the following about the right to access information:

"The applicant has the right to access information from the departments in accordance with the provisions of this law. The departments are obliged to make the information available to the applicant and the general public in accordance with the provisions of this law. (Justice, Ministry. 1393: Article 4).

Therefore, knowing is a fundamental human right on which other freedoms are based. Therefore, everyone should enjoy it. During the 1990s, with the rapid growth and development of information technology, the issue of access to the free flow of information took on a new form, and at the beginning of the 21st century, world leaders signed a statement pledging to create an information society in the new millennium.

The importance of the right to free access to information

Freedom of information and the press are fundamental human rights and a measure of all freedoms enshrined in the Charter of the United Nations and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, and are essential to the preservation and promotion of peace. This freedom is guaranteed when mass media personnel consistently and voluntarily strive to have the greatest sense of responsibility, to adhere deeply to the moral obligations arising from the need to be truthful and to seek the truth in their reports and to justify and interpret the facts. (Bakhtari, 1389: 58).

The present age is called the age of communication development, the age of information explosion and the age of globalization. New communication technologies and the astonishing and increasing development of mass media (media and super media) that have enabled people around the world to access the latest news and reports from the farthest corners of the world, have made the idea of a global village a reality. Is. This era has continued with the growth of industry and production of the modern world and the progress of telecommunication technology has accelerated and accelerated it. (Noorbakhsh, 1392: 113).

It is now so fast that satellite networks and the Internet have brought information to the moment. People all over the world are aware of the events, happenings and news at the moment of the incident. Although the free rotation of wealth and information is one of the most important characteristics of this age; But this rotation works when it is accompanied by a free circulation of power. Therefore, free economy, human rights and democracy are three inseparable components of this era. New citizenship rights are defined on these three bases. In the process, the traditional role of nation-states diminishes, racial boundaries, ethnic demarcations, and religious demarcations fade, and individuals defend their fundamental human rights in the future world based on a new definition of citizenship rights. The free flow of information is the basis of democracy, which has received special attention in the last three decades, and this attention stems from the fact that the stability and consistency of democracy in the current era is impossible without the free flow of information. For this reason, many scholars have mentioned the right of access and free dissemination of information to the oxygen of democracy. (Fanoos, 1392: 4).

Effects and benefits of the right to access information

The most important effects and benefits of the right to access information are as follows:

- 1- People's access to information.
- 2- Raising the insight, level of knowledge and awareness of the people about how to govern.
- 3- It strengthens people's trust in the government apparatus and encourages them to participate in national decisions and programs.

Therefore, paying attention to the concept of freedom of information and the right to access it is very important from the perspective of the relationship between people and political power, because access to information accelerates the process of innovation and initiative in society and identifies talents and matures them. And grows. On the other hand, power and information are organically and directly related to each other. A democratic system is possible when the extent of government power over its citizens is reduced. People's sovereignty is strengthened when the people are aware of the government's policies, programs and decisions and are able to react to them. Thus, the right to access information, on the one hand, creates the necessary mechanism for the realization of citizens' rights, and on the other hand, guarantees law-based behavior and the exercise of legitimate government power. (Qhazizadeh, 1387: 161).

Obstacles and challenges

Obstacles and Challenges to the Right to Information The fact that the right to freedom of information is not respected in some countries, especially in Afghanistan, and the exercise of this right always faces various challenges and difficulties, is related to several important issues:

1- Political Challenge:

The imposition of political restrictions by governments and governments is the most important factor in people's lack of access to government information. The type of system and political sovereignty and the belief in political power in a country have a direct and unequivocal impact on the way information flows in that country. Stable systems, stable and with an acceptable level of legitimacy, try to keep people informed about decisions, policies and programs in order to create transparency and strengthen the process of government agencies' accountability to the people and increase the level of legitimacy and trust of the people. Government and use the opinions of citizens to amend laws, procedures and legal decrees; On the contrary, weak regimes such as Afghanistan, with a low level of legitimacy, fear the free flow of information in their political realm and consider it dangerous for the security,

stability and stability of the system. For this reason, in such systems, the law of access to information faces many limitations and challenges.

2- Cultural Challenge:

In Afghanistan, as in other (developing) societies, people still have a low understanding of the law and a poor understanding of political and legal issues. People in these countries are unaware of the provisions of the law and do not know that How should they benefit from the provisions of the law in their interests, and this has created a kind of indifference of citizens to the implementation of the law.

3- Corruption and bureaucracy in the government:

Weakness of Afghan government departments can be a major challenge to law enforcement, especially the right to access information. Many laws are stuck in the maze of bureaucracy and are not enforced. In such countries, many laws have been passed and legally enforced; But in practice, the bureaucracy does not care about them or refuses to implement them.

Corruption in Afghanistan's government apparatus has also led to these agencies refusing to provide information to the people and creating obstacles to the legalization of freedom of information and its implementation; Because with the access of the people to information, all the administrative problems are revealed and this is not in the interest of power and economy in the body of the government, in this case, I refer to two examples of documentary and Tolo TV report:

<https://www.darivova.com/a/Afghanistan-information-access/3485056.html>

In one example: Journalists criticize the Supreme Court for not providing information to the media and for not cooperating with media outlets, saying: "Sometimes when we journalists want to include the view of the Supreme Court in our reports for weeks We are waiting. (Tolo News, News 6: 1/28/2020).

In the last year, cases have been sent by the prosecutor's office to the Supreme Court, or there have been other issues that the media have needed the opinion of the Supreme Court to follow up on; According to reporters, their work has failed due to the lack of information provided by the Supreme Court. The case of Karamuddin Karam, accused of abusing open soccer girls, Tamim Shansab for murder and clashes with security forces, and several other cases, transfer of money based on an unofficial document from the Central Bank to the Ministry of Finance and the Supreme Court, they are lost. Regarding the non-cooperation of the institutions with the media community of the country, some journalists have the following opinion: Reza Shahir: We are facing a problem in obtaining information from the Supreme Court. Mirwais Salam Zoi Reporter: This is really a serious problem. (Tolo News, News 6: 1/28/2020).

In another example: Transparency International Afghanistan: accuses the Afghan government of negligence in implementing the law on access to information, and its chief executive, Ikram Afzali, says: "There are serious restrictions on access to information in the Afghan government. The Right to Information Commission also operates under the influence of the government, although the Commission denies the right to access information. (Tolo News, News 6: 5 February 2020).

Reporters in Afghanistan say that the content of information provided to journalists by government agencies is incomplete and that even complete information is not available to government spokespersons.

Meanwhile, Amnesty International says the Afghan government must ensure that the people of Afghanistan have access to all the information necessary for the realization of human rights and that the authorities are accountable for their actions. The head of the US embassy in Kabul, NATO's civilian mission in Afghanistan, and Hanif Atmar, a former national security adviser, have called on the Afghan government to work for democracy in Afghanistan and to work for democracy in Afghanistan. Former President Hamid Karzai: He is also concerned about the restriction of the right of access to information and considers it contrary to the laws of the country. (Tolo News, News 6: 5 February 2020).

research findings

Quantitative results:

In this regard, a number of (3) related questions have been raised, which have been distributed to journalists under the ages of 20 to over 35 years. It should be noted, however, that this research includes journalists, Ney, and other journalists and journalists and experts in the field. The results and findings of these questionnaires are as follows.

Age? Please single mark an answer.

A: 18-25 = 30

B: 25-30 = 12

C: 30 -35 = 6

D: 35 to up = 3

Gender? Please single mark an answer.

A: Male = 32

B: Female = 15

Job? Please single mark an answer.

A: Aware of journalistic issues = 9

B: Reporter = 38

Part II:

1. How do you assess the situation of freedom of expression in Afghanistan?

A: Very good = 3 **B:** Good = 2 **C:** Medium = 19 **D:** Severe = 8 **E:** Very severe = 0

2- How much do you think the Afghan government has supported journalists?

A: Very good = 1 **B:** Good = 16 **C:** Medium = 22 **D:** Severe = 12 **E:** Very severe = 0

3. How much do the officials want to make information about their performances available to the people, especially the media?

A: Very high = 0 **B:** High = 7 **C:** Medium = 20 **D:** Low = 20 **E:** Very low = 6

4- In your opinion, what is the reason that the officials do not want or are not interested in providing information about their performance?

A: Corruption = 14 **B:** Lack of knowledge = 7 **C:** Non-commitment = 6

D: Underemployment = 12 **E:** lack of planning = 13

5. Do you see the right of political will in the government to access information to enforce the law?

A: Yes = 20

B: No = 31

Discussion

The free rotation of information is the basis of democracy, which has received special attention in the last three decades, and this attention stems from the fact that the stability and consistency of democracy in the current era is impossible without the free flow of information. For this reason, many scientists have mentioned the right of free access and dissemination of information to the oxygen of democracy (Fanoos, 1392: 4).

At present, the role of free media in informing and reflecting facts can be positively assessed. People now listen more to the local media and try to get information through the local media. This shows the fact that the local media has been able to gain the trust of their audiences, and on the other hand, due to the pluralism of society, it has become impossible for the government and influential people to hide the truth. Information is clearly present in the country, this problem, which is mostly created for journalists by government officials and government officials in general, has caused information to reach people unilaterally, especially in the current situation, and that is to hide the profile is the truth.

The problem of tendency to focus on policies within the organization, in addition to the problem of lack of access to information is also a serious problem, the tendency of a number of media and media people to parties, ethnicities or languages that this itself causes A number of media outlets and media workers have acted on their own to reflect the biased facts rather than the real and truth-based Mujib Khalwatgar, head of media at OSI.

But some media outlets trying to maintain their neutrality and partisanship are trying to get the information to the public: Abdul Hamid Mubarez, president of the National Union of Journalists of Afghanistan.

Article 50 of the Constitution of Afghanistan authorizes the citizens of Afghanistan to have access to public information. This article states: "Citizens of Afghanistan have the right to access information from government departments within the limits of the law. "There is no limit to the damage to the rights of others and public security. The citizens of Afghanistan are accepted into the service of the government on the basis of their competence and without any discrimination and in accordance with the provisions of the law" (Justice, Ministry. 2003: Article 50).

Although freedom of expression and the right of citizens to access information are recognized in the Afghan constitution; But due to the lack of a legal mechanism, this right has been ignored by government agencies and private institutions. Journalists also need reliable and accurate information to cover news and reports related to domestic issues, and this information should be provided to government officials by

the media, which unfortunately has not been the case so far, and government officials have always refused to provide Information has been denied to the media. For this reason, journalists and media outlets have always criticized the actions of government officials in this regard, calling their refusal to provide information to the public a violation of human rights, a violation of the constitution, and a violation of the principle of freedom of expression. In 2016, President Ghani issued a legislative decree ordering all government departments to comply with the provisions of the Right to Information Act and to provide the necessary information to the media; But again, these orders did not work out as expected.

The work of informing in many countries, especially in critical countries, and in particular Afghanistan, where government officials have no habit of providing information that is the right of citizens to the media; Mir Abdul wahed Hashemi, the head of the Ney Cultural Institute, has sometimes even caused the deaths, arrests and threats of journalists.

Conclusion

There is no doubt that access to information is one of the major challenges in developing countries, including Afghanistan. Governments deny citizens access to information for a variety of reasons, including the confidentiality of information and the protection of national interests and national security or the protection of privacy. Legal restrictions and monitoring of the right of access to information in a way that does not harm the rights of citizens are provided for in the laws of countries. As the government has a responsibility to respect the rights of the people, it also has a duty to protect the rights of individuals in society. Therefore, information that disrupts public order or violates the rights of individuals is not available to the public.

Therefore, the government can limit the access of citizens to information in several cases and prevent their dissemination:

1. Confidential and classified information that endangers the public interest and public security.
2. Disclosure of documents and information that are considered a violation of the privacy of the people and violate the privacy of citizens and damage the rights and relationships of individuals in society.
- 3- Disclosure of documents and information that are contrary to social ethics and contrary to the physical and mental health of society.
4. Documents and information that promote racist and ethnocentric ideas or are contrary to public decency.

At present, although we have the constitution and freedom of expression and the right of access to information and legislative decrees to implement it, the prohibitions on the rotation of information are also specified by the law mentioned above, but it is unfortunate that Officials in the country's political system are not only reluctant to provide information about their performances to the public, but in some cases prevent them from providing information. Again, the people and the media face the same problems as before and are deprived of the right to access information.

Therefore, in the current situation and in order for citizens to have the right to access information, in addition to the adoption of the law, several other issues should be considered, which have been addressed in the topic of suggestions.

Suggestions

In terms of suggestions, this study refers to the following suggestions in order to solve the problem of non-compliance with the law on the right of access to information in the country.

1- There is a need for the general government to classify documents and information in the departments and to separate confidential documents related to national security issues and public interests and territorial integrity from other documents and information.

2- An awareness-raising procedure should be prepared that is executive, and explain the duties and responsibilities of the officials and employees of the departments in this field.

3. The structural problems of the implementation of the law on the right of access to information must be identified and eliminated. Many laws need their own context to be enforced. It seems that in Afghanistan, due to the traditional bureaucratic system and the low capacity of government employees, the necessary structures to implement such laws have not yet been provided.

4. The implementation of this law requires an extensive training program during which, on the one hand, officials and employees of government departments are made aware of their responsibilities in relation to this law, and on the other hand, people and journalists have access to the provisions of the law. They are aware of the information, its benefits and limitations, and they can claim their rights only within the framework of the law and have no additional expectations from the government.

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